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Evaluation of change in approach to problem solving through developing spatial thinking

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we examine the transfer of spatial skills training to the ability to solve word problems in mathematics. A sample of freshman engineering students was recruited from an engineering school in the US consisting of 53 participants, 28 female and 25 male, categorized as 'weak visualizers' based on a spatial ability test. Of these, 30 (18 female, 12 male) enrolled in a spatial skills training course delivered during the autumn semester and the remaining 23 participants (10 female, 13 male) did not take this course. All participants were administered a spatial skills test and a measure of math problem solving ability at the beginning and end of the semester. Both those enrolled and not enrolled on the course made significant gains on the spatial ability measure but the gain was significantly higher for those enrolled on the course. No significant differences in the math pre and post-test scores were found for either group. Transfer of improvements in spatial ability to math problem solving ability were not manifest in this case.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Mathematics and Engineering Education, Gender and Diversity

Keywords: Spatial ability, problem solving, cognitive development

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INTRODUCTION

“I stand at the window of a railway carriage which is travelling uniformly, and drop a stone on the embankment, without throwing it. Then, disregarding the influence of the air resistance, I see the stone descend in a straight line. A pedestrian who observes the misdeed from the footpath notices that the stone falls to earth in a parabolic curve”. (Einstein, 1920, p. 8)

Conceptions of general intelligence evolved over the 20th century from unitary models such as Intelligent Quotient (IQ) to more complex multi-dimensional models that allowed for individual expression of strengths and weaknesses across a range of cognitive abilities (Andrade & May, 2004). Spatial ability has long been regarded as one of those dimensions (e.g. Thurstone, 1938) and while initially receiving less attention than other dimensions such as verbal, memory and perceptual abilities, its importance as a factor in the structure of human intelligence is being increasingly acknowledged (Johnson & Bouchard, 2005). Spatial ability is now regarded as an extremely important component of our overall cognitive ability that profoundly influences human performance in many roles and contexts.

Indeed, many famous scientists have been categorised as highly visual thinkers (Lohman, 1996). As Einstein’s quote above shows, he relied heavily on visualizing scenarios to create hypotheses he would then test on the journey towards his theories of relativity. The works he is most famous for emanated from thought experiments that were highly visual in nature as compared to the more mathematically focused efforts of his later years (Isaacson, 2007). These scientists created the scientific principles and theories that we expect science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) students to master. This is an arguably easier task for those students who are also highly visual thinkers whereas those students who enter STEM education with weak spatial abilities face a greater challenge in grasping these concepts.

It is unusual to see spatial skills development formally included in the STEM curriculum. Compare this with mathematical skills which are formally developed throughout the STEM curriculum and often further enhanced by math learning support centres. There are exceptions to this rule, an example being a group of US engineering schools who recently added spatial skills development to the curriculum through their participation in ENGAGE Engineering, a National Science Foundation funded project that began in 2009 (“ENGAGE Engineering,” n.d.). Their motivation was to improve retention rates of low spatial ability students based on findings from Michigan Technological University (MTU) [1]. Over a period of several years, students with initially weak spatial skills at MTU who participated in an intervention course consistently earned higher grades and graduated at higher rates than students similar in spatial ability who did not participate in the intervention course [2].

While improvements in retention following completion of the course are very encouraging it is not immediately clear how spatial skills training leads to improvements in retention rates and grades. Changes may occur in cognitive and/or affective domains, each of which encompasses a broad range of attributes and abilities. A cognitive ability that is reusable across the engineering curriculum is the ability to represent and solve problems and it was hypothesized that spatial thinking might play an important role in problem solving and that improvement in retention as a result of spatial skills training could be attributed, in part, to improved problem solving skills. The purpose of this paper is to address this hypothesis by examining the impact of the aforementioned spatial skills training course on the ability to solve story problems in mathematics. The study was conducted with participants from first year engineering at Ohio State University (OSU) in the fall semester of 2016.

1 LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 Spatial ability

Spatial ability came to prominence as a factor of intelligence through the work of Thurstone [3] who listed ‘spatial visualization’ as one of seven primary factors of intelligence. What exactly the factors of intelligence are, or, indeed, whether intelligence is best modelled as a set of factors at all is a matter of much discussion, e.g. , [4], but studies that are based within the factor analytic or psychometric tradition consistently identify three dominant human abilities – verbal, quantitative and spatial ability [5]. No more than the challenge of defining intelligence, spatial ability is a construct that has been hard to capture and over the years has been subdivided into different factors with an even greater number of ways of testing each factor and confusion as to which factor or factors a test belongs to. As noted recently by Uttal et al. (2013, p. 353), “*unfortunately, the definition of spatial ability is a matter of contention, and a comprehensive account of the underlying processes is not currently available.*” Despite this confusion, it is clear that spatial ability is a key aspect of human intelligence and, therefore, likely to play a key role in education.

This key role was highlighted by an analysis [6] of data collected from Project Talent, a study that collected a broad set of psychometric data from 400,000 high school participants and was conducted in the US in the 1960s [7]. Included was a follow up questionnaire distributed 11 years later to determine which, if any, higher education degree awards had been obtained by the participants. Wai et al. [6] focused on the three key abilities which they labelled as verbal, math and spatial and grouped the Project Talent sample based on higher education discipline and level of award. They found marked differences in high school ability profiles between those who were destined to pursue higher education in fields such as engineering versus humanities. Compared to the humanities group, a large difference in math ability was found in favour of the engineering group but the biggest difference was revealed by the spatial measure. Together, math and spatial abilities appeared to act as a filter for both career choice and success in higher education in the 1960s.

1.2 Problem Solving

Project Talent data did not indicate where in the STEM curriculum one is rewarded for having strong spatial ability. A significant relationship between scores on the Force Motion Concept Evaluation (FMCE), an assessment of conceptual understanding of Newtonian mechanics [8], and measures of spatial ability have been reported [9], [10]. The FMCE is a test of reasoning about force and motion using scenarios similar to Einstein’s thought experiment provided at the start of this paper. Similarly, scores on a test of electric circuits concepts called DIRECT [11] have been found to correlate significantly with tests of mental transformation and spatial visualization with the correlation almost entirely explained by questions related to physical aspects of circuits [12]. In chemistry education, spatial ability has been found to be significantly related to tasks that require problem solving [13]. In a meta-analysis, the highest correlations between math tests and spatial ability occurred for math tests that required a significant element of reasoning and the spatial test was mental rotation [14].

1.3 Research question

A common theme linking these studies was the need for some form of problem solving in each of the measures of subject knowledge. It was therefore decided to address this research question:

To what extent does a short course on spatial skills development transfer to changes in problem solving ability for both male and female participants?

Gender was included because research studies have consistently found gender to be a factor in spatial ability with males outperforming females on tests of mental rotation in particular [15].

2 RESEARCH DESIGN

2.1 Instruments

The PSVT:R (Guay, 1976) consists of 30 multiple choice questions designed to measure 3-D mental rotation ability. One of the two practice questions provided at the start of the test is shown in Figure 2. This question involves the rotation of the object by 90° around the vertical axis. The participant must apply the same rotation to the second figure and select from one of the 5 options below a match of the rotated figure. There are 30 questions on the test with variation in the number of axes involved in the rotation and the type of figure the participant must mentally rotate. The test is timed so both speed and accuracy are assessed. Reliability measures for the PSVT:R are reported by (Yoon, 2011) with Cronbach's $\alpha = .81$ measured using data collected from a sample of 180 education major undergraduate students enrolled in mathematics courses. The PSVT:R was selected as it has been used in previous studies of spatial skills development among engineering students [add ref after review].

Figure 2-1. A sample question on the PSVT:R [16]

Two sets of math problems, pre and post-test, were prepared for this study. The pre-test contained 8 problems that were obtained in various ways from internet searches of math tuition websites to a database of math problems prepared by the University of Limerick. The post-test was created from the pre-test by changing the quantities used in each problem but keeping the mathematical competencies, format, style and nature of question as consistent as possible. A trial run with some of these problems had revealed a significant correlation with spatial ability [add ref after review]. Forty five minutes were allowed in both the pre and post-tests to complete the problems. Reliability was measured using Cronbach's alpha and found to be .360 for the pre-test and .520 for the post-test. These are both low values and indicate there is little correlation between the different questions on the test with each other, particularly for the pre-test. In other words, performance on one question is a poor predictor of performance on another, at least in the context of this sample of participants.

2.2 Method

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board at the university who requested that all participants be fully informed about the study before consenting to participate. The sample was drawn from students who were enrolled in first year engineering at OSU 2016/2017 and who were identified as weak visualizers based on their score on the PSVT:R that was administered during the orientation phase in the summer of 2016. Those who scored 18 or lower on the 30 item PSVT:R were categorised as weak visualizers and were advised by their academic department to

enrol in the spatial skills training course in the fall semester. At the very beginning of the semester a request for volunteers to participate in this study was issued to all weak visualizers including those who opted out of the course. In total, 53 responded to the request, 30 (18 female, 12 male) of whom were enrolled in the spatial skills course and 23 (10 female, 13 male) who were not. All were invited to attend a problem solving observation at the beginning of the semester (August 2016) and again at the end of the semester (December 2016). After each session they were remunerated for their efforts with a gift voucher.

The format for each problem solving session was the same. Each participant booked an individual time slot and, on arrival, informed consent was obtained. The set of math problems was administered in two parts. A think aloud observation was made for the first five problems that lasted 30 minutes. A break then occurred during which the participant was fitted with an electroencephalogram (EEG) hat so that EEG data could be recorded while the participant solved the remaining three problems in silence. EEG data were required for a connected study. PSVT:R data collected during the orientation were entered as pre-test results and post-test data were collected at the end of the semester by administering the same PSVT:R test in class for those enrolled in the course and after the problem solving session for those who did not enrol.

2.3 Data Analysis

Data consisted of scores from the PSVT:R pre and post-test and solutions to each individual problem on the math pre and post-tests. Each math problem was scored as correct or incorrect with some discretion used in the definition of correct – if the answer was incorrect because of a minor computational error at the end then it was scored as correct. The problem scores were added to provide a math test score for each test with a range of 0 to 8. Descriptive statistics were then calculated for each measure. Differences within and between groups were calculated using paired and independent samples t-tests to determine changes between and from pre to post-tests. Correlations using the Pearson method, were determined between each variable. A factorial repeated-measures ANOVA was conducted to determine the significance of test time and spatial skills training on both the PSVT:R and math tests and to also check for any interaction between gender and training

3 RESULTS

3.1 Pre to post-test statistical comparisons

The sample was grouped by enrolment in the course and changes in each measure – PSVT:R and math problem solving – from pre to post-testing were determined within each grouping using a paired samples t-test (*Table 1*) and between each grouping using an independent samples t-test (*Table 2*).

No statistical difference between the PSVT:R pre-test scores of the two groups were observed implying they were equal in spatial ability at the beginning of the semester. Both groups scored significantly higher on the PSVT:R post-test but the gain was higher for those who enrolled in the course – they finished the semester with a mean PSVT:R of 23.07, significantly higher than that of the group who did not enrol whose mean PSVT:R post-test score was 20.61. They finished the semester at different levels of spatial ability. With regard to problem solving, there was no difference between the two groups on the math pre-test but this situation remained unchanged at post-test math scores, both in terms of mean scores and difference between means. Neither group made a significant improvement in the math score from pre to post-test. While the group that did not enrol on the course have a slightly higher post-test math

score it is not significantly different to that of the group that did enrol. Correlations between the measures were checked next to determine the significance of the relationship between math and spatial abilities at each time of testing. These were calculated based on the Pearson correlation coefficient and are presented in *Table 3*.

Table 1. Paired samples t-tests of post to pre-test scores.

	n	PSVT:R Pre M (SD)	PSVT:R Post M (SD)	t-test (p)	Math Pre M (SD)	Math Post M (SD)	t-test (p)
All	53	16.58 (3.86)	22.00 (4.55)	8.266 (.000)	2.17 (1.50)	2.30 (1.60)	.599 (.552)
Spatial training	30	16.33 (3.94)	23.07 (4.35)	7.697 (.000)	2.03 (1.52)	2.00 (1.51)	-.101 (.920)
No training	23	16.91 (3.80)	20.61 (4.52)	4.173 (.000)	2.35 (1.50)	2.70 (1.66)	1.283 (.213)

Table 2. Independent samples t-test of pre-test and post-test scores.

	Spatial training (n=30)	No training (n=23)	t-test
PSVT:R Pre	16.33 (3.94)	16.91 (3.80)	.539 (.592)
PSVT:R Post	23.07 (4.35)	20.61 (4.52)	-2.004 (.050)
Math Pre	2.03 (1.52)	2.35 (1.50)	.752 (.456)
Math Post	2.00 (1.51)	2.70 (1.66)	1.591 (.118)

Table 3. Correlations between the math and spatial abilities measures.

	PSVT:R Post	Math Pre	Math Post
PSVT:R Pre	.366**	.424**	.173
PSVT:R Post		.093	.034
Math Pre			.466**

The correlation between the pre and post-test scores on the PSVT:R was measured to be $r(51) = .366$ ($p < .01$). This is relatively small for two measures of the same test but can be explained by the significant change (improvement) in the test scores, i.e. participants responded very differently the second time. For the math tests, the correlation between them was measured to be $r(51) = .466$ ($p < .01$), which indicates some variation shared (22%) between the two measurements. In the case of problem solving, there was no significant change in the test scores from pre to post. With regard to correlations between the math and spatial tests at the two times, values of $r(51) = .424$ ($p < .01$) and $.034$ (N.S.) were measured for pre and post events respectively. A sizeable and significant correlation observed at pre-testing was completely diminished at post-testing.

3.2 Interaction between gender and spatial skills training on spatial and math

Based on the results from a factorial repeated-measures ANOVA, we found significant main effects of test time on the PSVT:R scores ($F(1,49) = 62.84$, $p < .001$). There was also a significant interaction effect between test time and spatial skills training ($F(1,49) = 5.633$, $p < .05$) which indicates that the spatial skills course had a significant effect on the spatial test scores. There was no significant interaction between test time and gender ($F(1,49) = .074$, $p = .787$) nor was there a significant interaction between test time, training and gender ($F(1,49) = 2.783$, $p = .102$). With regard to math pre and post-test scores, nothing of significance was found using the repeated-measures

ANOVA – neither test time nor interactions with training and gender were found to be significant.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Significant gains in spatial ability were made between pre and post-tests by both groups, those who did and didn't enrol in the spatial skills training course. However, the group that enrolled made a significantly higher gain than those who didn't. It appears that the passage of one semester at OSU first year engineering leads to improved spatial ability while the passage of time plus spatial skills training leads to even greater improvement in spatial ability. Others have observed gains in spatial tests over time in the absence of focused training and have attributed this to a practice effect, i.e. one becomes better simply by taking the test a second time [17]. This hypothesis might be supported by the finding that independent samples of students on all four years of Bachelor of Electrical Engineering programme were found to be equal in spatial ability [12]. That paired samples reveal improvement over time but independent samples do not lends some credence to the practice effect idea. If so, then the group who did not enrol have improved because of test practice and not spatial ability whereas the group who did enrol have improved because of both practice and improved ability.

No significant changes, either positive or negative, were observed in math problem solving and it therefore appears that improvements in spatial ability did not transfer to improvements in solving math story problems. Either transfer is possible but was not found in this case or transfer is not possible. The former could be explained by the poor reliability ratings of the math pre and post-tests leading to excessive scatter in the data – in their appearing to the participants these math questions require so many different skills that a pattern related to spatial ability failed to emerge. Although all the problems are relatively straightforward – they are of PISA standard [18] – and have one correct answer, the results contained much variation in the success rates of each problem pair, as shown in *Table 4*. In parentheses in column three are the number of participants who got either the corresponding pre-test or post-test problem correct.

Problem Name Pre/Post	Incorrect on both	Correct on 1 (pre/post)	Correct on both
1 Rain/Engine Oil	31	20 (3/17)	2
2 Jars/Strawberries	16	19 (7/12)	18
3 Blood/Cylinders	29	19 (16/3)	5
4 Track/Earth Band	33	18 (1/17)	2
5 HCl/Salad Dressing	38	11 (5/6)	4
6 Lawn/Picture Frame	33	19 (13/6)	1
7 Jug 1/Jug 2	17	22 (8/14)	14
8 Cans 1/Cans 2	37	15 (15/0)	1

Table 4. Success rates by test and problem.

For problems 1, 3, 4, and 8 the difference in success rates is greater than 10 (out of 53). For five problem pairs, more participants were correct on the post than pre-test version of the problem, e.g. problem 1, while for the other three, the reverse was true. If practice effects occurred in the math test they were limited to so few problems that they cannot be observed in the total problem scores. The lack of transfer could also be explained by insufficient time spent on spatial skills training or that different aspects of the training need to be emphasised to maximise the transfer to problem solving.

Alternatively, transfer between spatial skills training and problem solving improvement is not possible but this seems at odds with significant relationship that was observed between spatial ability and problem solving. However, correlation does not imply

causation, the latter necessary for improvement in one variable to cause change in the other. To follow this line of thought raises the possibility of a third unknown variable that is common to both and provides a reason for the correlation. In the literature review it was established that spatial ability is a key factor in STEM education and that tests of mental rotation such as the PSVT:R are relevant to non-routine problem solving and reasoning. We therefore feel it is justified to conduct a more qualitative analysis of the pre/post data to examine the problem solving process in more detail and search for aspects that may not have been revealed to date.

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